

ISOMERIC TRIAZOCINNAMIC ACIDS AND RELATED COMPOUNDS

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Nuclear substituted *triazocinnamic* and triazobenzoic acids have been prepared and their properties, with relative stabilities, investigated. The triazocinnamic acids give on oxidation the corresponding triazobenzoic acids and on reduction, different products depending on the agent employed. With concentrated sulphuric acid, the triazocinnamic acids and *p*-triazobenzoic acid evolve two-thirds of the nitrogen content, the *o*- and *m*-triazobenzoic acids yielding a quantity of nitrogen which approximates more closely to one-half rather than two-thirds of the nitrogen content. Formation of carbon monoxide, which is unusual, was noticed during these decompositions. A striking difference in the comparative stabilities of the two series towards sulphuric acid of different strengths was brought to light by these experiments. The *para*-derivative is the least stable in the cinnamic acid series, whereas it is the most stable in the benzoic acids. This is probably due to the different orienting influences of the original substituents in the two series. *Methyl o*-triazocinnamate has been prepared and its properties examined.

Aromatic triazo compounds have been subjected to many reactions involving decomposition, reduction and addition. In the present investigation, the nuclear substituted *triazocinnamic acids* and triazobenzoic acids have been prepared and their relative stabilities as well as other reactions studied. The triazocinnamic acids were prepared from the corresponding aminocinnamic acids by diazotisation and double decomposition with sodium azide, the amino-acids themselves being obtained from the nitro-acids by reduction.

It is of interest to record the formation of a small quantity of an *acidic substance* decomposing at 268-70° during the preparation of *m*-triazocinnamic acid. The *o*- and *p*-nitrocinnamic acids were formed in almost equal

quantities by the nitration of cinnamic acid at 8-10° (cf. Müller, *Annalen*, 1882, 212, 124) and were conveniently separated through their methyl esters, the ester of the *o*-nitro-acid being more soluble in methyl alcohol than the ester of the *p*-isomer. The triazobenzoic acids which have been prepared by Bamberger and de Werra (*Ber.*, 1902, 35, 3718) by the interaction of the diazonium perbromides with ammonia, were more conveniently obtained by us from the appropriate aminobenzoic acids by diazotisation and interaction of the diazonium salt with sodium azide

A cold dilute solution of potassium permanganate converts the triazocinnamic acids into the corresponding triazobenzoic acids. The isomers behave differently, however, on reduction. The *m*- and *p*-acids on reduction with tin and hydrochloric acid or yellow ammonium sulphide give the corresponding aminocinnamic acids, while with sodium amalgam, aminohydrocinnamic acids are formed. The behaviour of *o*-triazocinnamic acid on reduction is slightly different. With ammonium sulphide, simple reduction of the triazo group occurs resulting in the formation of *o*-aminocinnamic acid (VI) and with tin and hydrochloric acid, carbostyryl (VII) is formed, ring-closure taking place. On a more drastic reduction with sodium amalgam, dihydrocarbostyryl (VIII) results, thus indicating that any of the three reduction products can be obtained by varying the reducing agent employed.

Hot 12 % potassium hydroxide has no appreciable action on *o*- and *m*-triazocinnamic acids, whereas in the case of the *p*-isomer, although a

part of the substance is recovered unchanged after 4 hours, there is produced a compound which does not melt or decompose up to 320° . It is known that aromatic triazo derivatives show a remarkable stability towards cold potassium hydroxide solution; on the other hand, under similar conditions, the aliphatic as well as cyclic non-benzenoid triazo compounds decompose very rapidly (Forster and Fierz, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1908, 93, 73; Forster and Judd, *ibid.*, 1910, 97, 255, 257). The decomposition of *p*-triazocinnamic acid is probably due to the well known influence of a *para*-orienting group on the *para*-substituent; in this instance, the crotonyl group, $-\text{CH}=\text{CH}\cdot\text{COOH}$ makes the triazo group in the *para*-position unstable (*cf.* Forster and Fierz, *ibid.*, 1907, 91, 1356). Resinification occurred when the triazocinnamic acids were boiled with 40% aqueous potash, the triazo group being destroyed in the process.

Triazo compounds on treatment with concentrated sulphuric acid are known to yield two-thirds of their nitrogen (*cf.* Forster and Müller, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1910, 97, 132, 137, 141). The three triazocinnamic acids and *p*-triazobenzoic acid also evolve two-thirds of the nitrogen content on being treated with strong sulphuric acid; *o*- and *m*-triazobenzoic acids, however,

FIG. 1.
Triazocinnamic acids.

FIG. 2.
Triazobenzoic acids.

yield a smaller quantity of nitrogen, approximating more closely to half rather than two-thirds of the content of the element, the figures are not being sufficiently definite to admit of any general conclusion being drawn as to the course of the reaction. Such abnormalities have been observed in other cases also, especially by Forster and Fierz (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1908, 93, 79). An unusual feature of the decomposition of the triazo-acids used in the present investigation was the formation of carbon monoxide in addition to the usual products of decomposition, probably due to the presence of the unsaturated complex.

The comparative stabilities of isomeric triazocinnamic and triazobenzoic acids were studied by determining the temperature of decomposition with sulphuric acid of different strengths. The relation between the two was found to be a simple inverse linear function in all the cases as is evident from Figs. 1 and 2. It may be noted that the stability with reference to sulphuric acid increases from *para* to *ortho* in the triazocinnamic acid series, the *m*-isomer being intermediate; the triazobenzoic acids, on the other hand, display surprisingly enough, a reverse order of stability, which increases from *ortho* to *para*, that of the *m*-isomer again occupying an intermediate position. It will be noticed that the *para*-derivative is the least stable in the cinnamic acid series, whereas it is the most stable in the benzoic acids. This is probably due to the different orienting influences of the original substituents in the two series; the *para*-orienting group in the cinnamic acids makes the *para*-substituent unstable, while the carboxyl group is mainly *meta*-orienting in the benzoic acid series, although if this were the chief factor in determining stability, the *meta*-isomer should be the least stable in the latter case.

(IX)

(X)

Attempts to prepare either α - (IX) or β - triazocinnamic acids (X) (Forster and Rao, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 1946) whose examination would be of interest for more than one reasons have not been successful. Not only would they contain a triazo group attached to a doubly linked carbon atom, but their possible conversion into α - or β -aminocinnamic acids would yield a rare class of substances. Replacement of the hydroxy group in α -triazo- β -hydroxy- β -phenylpropionic acid, $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5 \cdot \text{CHOH} \cdot \text{CHN}_2 \cdot \text{COOH}$ (XI) by a halogen

through the use of different halogenating reagents and subsequent removal of a molecule of hydrogen halide from the resulting substance did not meet with success. The compound (XI), which has been prepared by Forster and Saville (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 2598) by the interaction of cinnamic acid chlorohydrin, $C_6H_5 \cdot CHOH \cdot CHCl \cdot COOH$ (XII) and sodium azide in aqueous solution was obtained in this instance by using the bromohydrin instead of the chlorohydrin. The former is obtained in better yield when prepared under conditions used by Forster and Saville (*loc. cit.*) for the preparation of (XII), than by the original method of Berner and Riiber (*Ber.*, 1921, 54, 1954), considerable quantities of ω -bromostyrene being produced in the latter method, although the original authors do not record it. Synthesis of (IX) by the condensation of benzaldehyde with ethyl triazoacetate did not succeed.

On refluxing a mixture of cinnamic acid dibromide, in alcohol-pyridine and an aqueous solution of sodium azide, ω -bromostyrene and an acidic substance (m. p. 217°) containing nitrogen, but no triazo group was obtained. Owing to insufficiency of material, the constitution of this substance, whose dibromide melted at 176° , could not be determined. In view of the ease with which decarboxylation takes place when derivatives of the free acid are used, the action of sodium azide on the methyl ester of cinnamic acid dibromide was studied. An oil containing a triazo group as well as bromine was formed by this reaction, and gave on treatment with pyridine an unsaturated ester containing a triazo group. None of the liquids could be distilled without decomposition, even under reduced pressure. Although this ester could not be purified by distillation, it is clear from its properties and analysis that it is *methyl* α - (XIII) or β - triazocinnamate (XIV), probably the former.

(XIII)

(XIV)

EXPERIMENTAL.

Nitrocinnamic Acids.

The *o*- and *p*-nitro-acids were prepared by nitration of cinnamic acid at $8-10^\circ$ and separated through their methyl esters. The *m*-nitro-acid was obtained by the condensation of *m*-nitrobenzaldehyde with malonic acid in presence of pyridine and piperidine.

Triazocinnamic Acids.

Aminocinnamic acid (54 g.), prepared by the reduction of the nitro-acid was stirred in a beaker surrounded by ice with water (108 c.c.) and 25% hydrochloric acid (74.5 c.c.). A solution of sodium nitrite (12.7 g. in 20 c.c. of water) cooled to 0° was added in the course of ten minutes with constant stirring. The diazotised solution was allowed to stand in ice for twenty minutes, then treated with enough urea to destroy excess of nitrous acid. An aqueous solution of sodium azide (13.7 g. in 108 c.c. of water) was then added dropwise with constant stirring, the temperature being maintained at 0°. Vigorous evolution of nitrogen took place, frothing being controlled by adding small quantities of ether from time to time. After standing in ice for some time, the precipitated acid was filtered and purified, yield about 48 g. The dibromides were prepared by adding bromine in chloroform to a suspension of the triazo-acid in the same solvent. The triazo-acids do not detonate on heating but burn quietly with a vigorous flame. The *o*- and *p*-isomers display a tendency to decompose on keeping, characteristic of aromatic derivatives. The dibromides also exhibit a similar behaviour, the *m*-isomer being stable while the other two decompose on keeping.

o-Triazocinnamic acid crystallises from acetone (charcoal) in long needles melting at 186° (decomp.). (Found: N, 22.4; Equiv., 187. $C_9H_7O_2N_3$ requires N, 22.2 per cent. Equiv., 189). The acid is sparingly soluble in benzene but fairly soluble in chloroform. A solution of the acid in acetone exhibits green fluorescence. The acid and its solution in methyl alcohol are light brown in colour when freshly prepared, and darken on standing. While the acid was recovered unchanged after heating with 12% potash on the boiling water-bath for 4 hours, it was converted into a resinous product containing nitrogen but no triazole group on refluxing with a 40% solution of potassium hydroxide during 4 hours. *o*-Triazocinnamic acid dibromide separates from benzene in long, prismatic needles, m. p. 165-66° (decomp.). (Found: Br, 45.7. $C_9H_7O_2N_3Br_2$ requires Br, 45.8 per cent).

Oxidised by a cold 4% aqueous solution of potassium permanganate in alkaline solution. *o*-triazocinnamic acid was converted into *o*-triazobenzoic acid, which after crystallisation from hot water melts at 143-44°. (Found: N, 25.6. Equiv., 164. $C_7H_5O_2N_3$ requires N, 25.8 per cent. Equiv., 163). *o*-Triazocinnamic acid on reduction with yellow ammonium sulphide in ammoniacal solution gives *o*-aminocinnamic acid, m. p. 158°, identified with an authentic specimen, while with tin and warm hydrochloric acid, carbostyryl is formed, m. p. 199°. (Found: N, 9.8. Calc. for $C_{10}H_7ON$: N, 9.7

per cent). With sodium amalgam, however, dihydrocarbostyryl melting at 163° , and identified by comparison with an authentic specimen, is produced. (Found : N, 9.7. Calc. for C_9H_9ON N, 9.5 per cent).

m-Triazocinnamic acid separates from acetone in prismatic needles, m.p. 165° (decomp.). (Found : N, 22.4 %. Equiv., 190). The *dibromide* crystallised from benzene, m.p. 157° . (Found : Br, 45.6 %). Towards potassium hydroxide *m*-triazocinnamic acid resembles the *o*-isomer. On oxidation with dilute permanganate, the *m*-triazo-acid is converted into *m*-triazobenzoic acid crystallising from water in glistening needles, m.p. 160° . (Found : N, 26.0 %. Equiv., 164). Freshly prepared yellow ammonium sulphide reduces *m*-triazocinnamic acid to *m*-aminocinnamic acid, m.p. 180° , formed also by reduction with tin and hydrochloric acid. With sodium amalgam, however, reduction of the ethylenic bond also takes place yielding β -*m*-aminophenylpropionic acid, which crystallises from water or alcohol in needles, melting at 83° . (Found : N, 8.7. $C_9H_{11}O_2N$ requires N, 8.5 per cent).

A small quantity of an acetone-insoluble material is always formed during the preparation of *m*-triazocinnamic acid. After purification by dissolving in pyridine, filtering and precipitating by acidifying, this *acid* crystallises from water in prisms decomposing at $268-70^{\circ}$. (Found : C, 65.1; H, 4.9; N, 8.7 per cent. Equiv., 98).

p-Triazocinnamic acid, crystallised from acetone, decomposes at $195-96^{\circ}$ with slight decomposition at 160° . (Found : N, 22.5 %. Equiv., 188). The sodium salt is less soluble in water than the sodium salts of the *o*- and *m*-isomers. The *dibromide* crystallises from benzene in prisms, melting at $140-41^{\circ}$. (Found : Br, 45.5 %). It decomposes on keeping. On heating with 12% potash on a boiling water-bath for 4 hours, part of *p*-triazocinnamic acid is converted into a product which does not melt or decompose up to 320° . This substance is insoluble in low-boiling solvents, but soluble in nitrobenzene. A dark resinous material is formed from the triazo-acid on boiling with 40% potassium hydroxide. Dilute permanganate oxidises the triazo-acid to *p*-triazobenzoic acid, which, crystallised from water, melts at 180° . (Found : N, 25.9 %. Equiv., 164). On reduction with yellow ammonium sulphide or tin and hydrochloric acid, *p*-triazocinnamic acid gives *p*-aminocinnamic acid melting at 175° , while with sodium amalgam *p*-aminohydrocinnamic acid crystallising from water in long

The equivalent weights of *m*- and *p*-triazocinnamic acids were determined by carrying out the titration in benzene solution, with frequent and thorough shaking, as the end-point was not sharp in methyl alcohol.

brownish needles, m.p. 131°, is formed. (Found : N, 8·6%). The acetyl derivative of this amino- acid melts at 142°.

Triazobenzoic Acids.

The hydrochloride of the aminobenzoic acid (20 g.) was mixed with a solution of 25% hydrochloric acid (26 c.c.) in water (100 c.c.) and diazotised with a solution of sodium nitrite (9 g. in 24 c.c. of water) at 0°. Enough urea was added after 20 minutes to destroy the excess of nitrous acid and a solution of sodium azide (9·2 g. in 25 c.c. of water) was added drop-wise. The precipitated triazobenzoic acid was filtered after 1 hour in the ice-bath and purified, yield 22 g.

o-Triazobenzoic acid crystallises from warm water in long needles melting at 143°-44°. (Found : N, 25·7; Equiv., 165. $C_7H_5O_2N_3$ requires N, 25·8 per cent. Equiv., 163). *m*-Triazobenzoic acid crystallises from aqueous alcohol in prisms, m.p. 160°. (Found : N, 25·5 per cent. Equiv., 164). *p*-Triazobenzoic acid separates from aqueous alcohol in prismatic needles, m.p. 180-81°. (Found : N, 26·5 per cent. Equiv., 164).

Decomposition of the Triazo Compounds by Sulphuric Acid.

(a) *Measurement of the Volume of Nitrogen evolved.*—The reaction was carried out in a bottle of 100 c.c. capacity and the gases generated were slowly allowed to bubble through a solution of cuprous chloride in hydrochloric acid to remove carbon monoxide and finally collected over 30% aqueous potash in a Lunge nitrometer. The volume of gas was read after standing over the alkali for 1 hour.

TABLE I.

Wt. of the substance.	Gas collected.	Pressure (mm. Hg)/T.	Vol. at N. T. P.	‡ N. at N. T. P.
<i>o</i> -Triazocinnamic acid.				
0·0371g.	5·3 c.c.	764/27°	4·7 c.c.	4·4 c.c.
0·0699	10·3	„	9·2	8·3
0·1045	21·4	„	19·2	20·0
0·1890	26·8	„	23·5	22·4

TABLE I (contd.).

Wt. of the substance.	Gas collected.	Pressure (mm. Hg)/T.	Vol. at N. T. P.	$\frac{1}{2}$ N at N. T. P.
<i>m</i> -Triazocinnamic acid.				
0'1332 g.	17'6 c.c.	763/27°	15'7 c.c.	15'8 c.c.
0'1782	24'7	"	22'6	21'2
0'1898	24'6	"	21'9	22'5
0'2096	27'5	"	24'6	24'6
<i>p</i> -Triazocinnamic acid.				
0'0412	5'6	761/29°	4'9	4'9
0'0838	10'5	"	9'3	9'9
0'0844	10'7	"	9'5	9'9
0'0883	11'8	"	10'4	10'6
<i>o</i> -Triazobenzotic acid.				
0'0234	2'4	759/30'5°	2'1	3'2
0'0504	5'0	760/30°	4'4	6'9
0'0573	6'5	761/30	5'7	7'8
0'0588	7'3	759/30'5°	6'4	8'0
<i>m</i> -Triazobenzotic acid.				
0'0710	8'7	758'31°	7'6	9'7
0'0886	10'0	759/30'5°	9'2	12'1
0'0892	11'5	758'31°	10'0	12'2
0'1053	13'6	758'31°	11'9	14'4
<i>p</i> -Triazobenzotic acid.				
0'0376	5'7	762/29'5°	5'0	5'1
0'0428	6'8	"	6'0	5'9
0'0536	8'0	"	7'1	7'3
0'0820	12'4	"	11'0	11'2

(b) *Relation between Temperature of Decomposition and Concentration of Sulphuric Acid.*—For each experiment, 0'1 g. of the triazo-acid, finely powdered to pass through a 40 mesh gauze, was treated with 2 c. c. of sulphuric acid in a test-tube surrounded by two vessels with efficient

stirring arrangements to keep the temperature constant. The temperature of decomposition was noted when frothing started and gas was evolved. The temperature recorded in Table II is the mean of three experiments.

TABLE II.

Strength of acid wt. per cent.	Decomposition temperature		
	<i>ortho.</i>	<i>meta.</i>	<i>para.</i>
<i>Triazocinnamic Acid.</i>			
59	88.8°	79.8°	62.9°
64	74.5°	65.0°	50.5°
69	59.0°	50.5°	30.9°
74	44.9°	36.6°	Room temp.
79	30.5°	Rapid decomp. at room temp.	Rapid decomp. at room temp.
84	Rapid decomp. in the cold.		
<i>Triazobenzolic Acid.</i>			
39	82.1°	—	—
49	62.5°	—	—
59	41.5°	76.7°	89.7°
64	31.0°	64.6°	79.0°
69	Action in the cold, no charring.	52.5°	68.5°
74	„	40.6°	58.5°
79	Vigorous action, dark green soln. formed.	Slow action	48.4°
84	„	Immediate action	Vigorous reaction

Cinnamic bromohydrin (m. p. 125°), prepared by the interaction of solutions of sodium cinnamate and sodium hypobromite essentially under conditions used by Forster and Saville (*loc. cit.*) in the case of the chlorohydrin, was converted into α -triazobenzol- β -hydroxy- β -phenylpropionic acid (XI), m. p. 121°, by interaction with sodium azide in alkaline solution. While hot 48% hydrobromic acid had no action on the triazohydrin, 25% hydrochloric acid converted it into a tarry substance when boiled. There was considerable decomposition with thionyl chloride or phosphorus pentachloride or pentabromide.

Action of Sodium Azide on Cinnamic Acid Dibromide in presence of Pyridine.—A mixture of the finely powdered dibromide (10 g.), ethyl alcohol (55 c. c.) containing pyridine (5 c. c.) and a solution of sodium azide (2.8 g. in 20 c. c. of water) was refluxed for 3 hours. The residue after removing the major portion of the alcohol was treated with excess of dilute hydrochloric acid and the solid which separated on standing, was filtered, washed with a little petroleum ether after draining, pressed on a porous plate and crystallised from hot water when it separated in fine, hairy needles, m. p. 217°. (Found : C, 60.6; H, 4.0; N, 8.0%. Equiv., 144). It decolourises potassium permanganate and bromine water. Its *dibromide* crystallises from alcohol in prisms, m. p. 176° with previous softening at 171°. (Found : Br, 49.4%). From the mother liquor of the acid, small quantity of *o*-bromostyrene could be obtained.

Action of Sodium Azide on Methyl $\alpha\beta$ -Dibromo- β -phenylpropionate.—A mixture of the ester (20.6 g.), methyl alcohol (68 c. c.) and an aqueous solution of sodium azide (8 g. in 25 c. c.) was refluxed on the steam-bath for 14 hours, the original turbidity disappearing in 3 hours. The product obtained by the removal of most of the alcohol, was diluted with water, the solution saturated with common salt and the precipitated oil extracted with ether thrice. The combined ether extracts after drying over anhydrous calcium chloride and removal of solvent gave a pale, clear orange-coloured oil (12 g.) which produced effervescence with concentrated sulphuric acid and contained bromine. The oil (11 g.) was mixed with pyridine (8 c. c.) and heated on the water-bath. After 3 hours, during which period some pyridine hydrobromide had separated, the reaction mixture was cooled, acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid and the solution extracted with ether. On removing the solvent from the washed and dried ether extract an oil was obtained which by its properties and analysis can be *methyl α - or β -triazocinnamate* (XIII) or (XIV). (Found for the undistilled specimen after standing in the vacuum desiccator for some weeks : N, 21.6. $C_{10}H_9O_2N_3$ requires N, 20.71 per cent). The ester decolourises neutral potassium permanganate and bromine water and vigorously effervesces with concentrated sulphuric acid; but a dibromide could not be obtained. On oxidation with permanganate, partial conversion to benzoic acid occurred, indicating the position of the triazo group to be probably α .